

Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial studies of some copper(II) complexes with β -enaminones

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Abstract : Copper(II) complexes of the type [CuLX] (where HL represents an enaminone formed by condensation of a β -diketone viz. acetylacetone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane with 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene and X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, OAc⁻, ClO₄⁻ or SO₄²⁻) have been synthesised and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility measurements and various spectral studies. A β -ketoamine structure of the ligand and its bonding mode to the metal ion has been discussed on the basis of IR, UV and NMR spectral studies. The free ligands as well as the complexes have been screened for their antibacterial activity. The effect of co-ligand on antibacterial activity has been also discussed.

Keywords : β -Enaminones, copper(II) complexes, synthesis.

β -Enaminones form an interesting class of compounds which can be obtained by condensation of β -diketones with primary amines and find extensive applications in heterocyclic synthesis^{1,2}. However, ligational behaviour of this class of compounds has received comparatively less attention so far. Although metal complexes of enaminones derived from some β -diketones and primary amines have been investigated to certain extent, those derived from heterocyclic amines, particularly from aminothiophenes have received comparatively less attention. Generally, aminothiophenes are highly unstable, but they have been made stable by suitable substitution at the thiophene ring by Gewald synthesis³ and the resulting compound namely, 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[*b*]thiophene has been condensed with three different β -diketones viz. acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane to yield β -enaminones (abbreviated as Haat, Hbat and Hdmt respectively). The resulting three monobasic tridentate ligands containing ONO donor set have been used as prospective chelating agents for copper(II) ion. In this communication, we describe the synthesis, characterisation and antibacterial studies of some copper(II) complexes prepared from the above ligands and different co-ligands. Effect of the co-ligand on antibacterial activity has been also examined. The anion present in the coordination sphere of

[Cu(aat)Cl] was replaced by other anions like Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, OAc⁻, ClO₄⁻ or SO₄²⁻.

Results and discussion

The complexes obtained are listed in Table 1. All the complexes are fairly stable at room temperature. Formulation of these complexes has been made on the basis of their elemental analytical data, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility values. Molar conductance values of the complexes measured in DMF adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes⁴.

Structure of the ligand :

It has been reported⁵ that compounds containing -NH-C=C-C=O chromophore exhibits a characteristic band for π - π^* transition at *ca.* 330 nm. Ultraviolet spectrum of Haat exhibited a strong band at 325 nm, characteristic of the β -enaminone form. Corresponding bands for Hbat and Hdmt were observed at 335 nm and 338 nm respectively. This is a clear evidence that the ligands exist in the ketoenamine form rather than in the enolimine form (Fig. 1).

The above structure is further supported by NMR spectral data. Proton magnetic resonance spectrum of Haat recorded in CDCl₃ showed NH proton signal as a broad multiplet at δ 11.21. The low field shift of this signal is

Table 1. Analytical data and other details of Cu^{II} complexes of Haat containing different counter anions

Complex	Yield (%)	Analytical data (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Magnetic moment	Molar conductance (in DMF) $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
		Metal	C	H	N	S		
[Cu(aat)Cl]	72	15.30 (15.67)	44.55 (44.49)	4.50 (4.93)	3.30 (3.45)	7.76 (7.90)	1.97	11.3
[Cu(bat)Cl]	70	13.72 (13.59)	53.50 (53.96)	4.66 (4.71)	2.72 (2.79)	6.92 (6.85)	1.92	9.7
[Cu(dmt)Cl]	68	12.16 (12.32)	58.96 (58.97)	4.32 (4.53)	2.51 (2.64)	6.15 (6.04)	1.98	8.9
[Cu(aat)Br]	78	14.00 (14.15)	42.93 (42.80)	4.35 (4.45)	3.00 (3.12)	7.05 (7.13)	1.93	11.7
[Cu(aat)I]	65	12.95 (12.78)	38.75 (38.67)	3.97 (4.02)	2.80 (2.81)	6.39 (6.44)	1.90	10.5
[Cu(aat)NO ₃]	75	14.90 (14.71)	44.70 (44.49)	4.52 (4.63)	6.35 (6.48)	7.35 (7.41)	1.93	9.6
[Cu(aat)OAc]	65	15.00 (14.81)	50.50 (50.40)	5.15 (5.36)	3.10 (3.26)	7.15 (7.46)	1.91	7.6
[Cu(aat)ClO ₄]	80	13.70 (13.53)	40.62 (40.93)	4.05 (4.26)	2.82 (2.98)	6.66 (6.82)	1.95	13.5
[Cu(aat)SO ₄] _{1/2}	60	15.35 (15.20)	45.76 (45.98)	4.50 (4.79)	3.10 (3.35)	11.50 (11.49)	1.85	8.16

Haat = 2-[N-(2'-oxo-pent-3'-en-4'-yl)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene.

Hbat = 2-[N-(2'-oxo-1'-phenyl-2'-en-3'-yl)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene.

Hdmt = 2-[N-(1'-oxo-1',3'-diphenyl-prop-2'-en-3'-yl)amino]-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene.

R₁ = CH₃ or C₆H₅

R₂ = CH₃ or C₆H₅

Fig. 1

presumably due to strong internal hydrogen bonding and its breadth is due to quadrupole of the nitrogen nucleus. Sharp signals for methyl protons of the acetylaceton moiety have been observed around δ 2.91 and methylene proton \sim δ 3.71. But signals of methyl protons of the ester function have been merged with cyclohexane proton signal appearing around δ 1.13. On the basis of pro-

ton NMR spectral data, condensation products of β -diketones with primary amines have been shown previously to have similar β -enaminone structure⁶.

In agreement with the UV and NMR spectral data, infrared spectrum of Haat, showed a strong band at 1690 and 1630 cm^{-1} due to the ester carbonyl group and hydrogen bonded carbonyl group of the β -diketone moiety. As expected for a strongly hydrogen bonded NH, a broad band ranging from 3300–2850 cm^{-1} has been observed in the IR spectrum of this ligand. Aliphatic $\nu(\text{C-H})$ modes appearing \sim 2950 cm^{-1} are partly concealed by this broad $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band. Apart from this two medium intensity bands are also observed at 1540 and 1525 cm^{-1} . If any one of these bands is assigned to $\nu(\text{C-N})$, it would mean that the C-N bond order is between one and two. Hence it appears that the $\nu(\text{C-N})$ vibration is coupled with $\nu(\text{C=C})$ vibration⁷. The band at 1540 cm^{-1} is considered to have greater contribution from C-C and band at 1525 cm^{-1} has greater contribution from $\nu(\text{C-N})$. In agreement with this, the latter band showed characteristic upward shift (\sim 20 cm^{-1}) on complexation with metal ion.

The substituted thiophene ring vibrations of the ligands⁸ appear around 1500, 1420 and 1360 cm^{-1} . Structural features of Hbat and Hdmt are strikingly similar to those of Haat except that the benzoyl carbonyl band appeared at 1625 and 1620 cm^{-1} respectively and the ester carbonyl stretching frequencies have been observed at 1685 and 1680 cm^{-1} respectively. Thus the ligands exist in the ketoenamine form rather than the enolimine form and hence the condensation products are generally known as β -enaminones⁹.

Metal complexes :

Ultraviolet spectral band, characteristic of the ketoenamine form⁵ of the ligands is slightly red shifted in the spectra of the metal complexes. Hence it is evident that no structural alteration of the ligands occurs on chelation with metal ion i.e. in the metal chelates also the ligands exist in the β -enaminone form. The solid state spectrum of [Cu(aat)Cl] did not show any variation from that of the solution spectrum.

Infrared spectra of the metal chelates are closely similar among themselves (Table 2). Donor functions of the ligands involved in bonding to the metal ion have been determined by a careful comparison of the infrared spectra of the ligands and the complexes. Only those bands diagnostic of coordination are considered. In the IR spectra of the complexes all the characteristic bands of the ligands have been perturbed, indicating their involvement in chelation. Disappearance of the broad $\nu(\text{N-H})$ band of the ligands clearly indicates the replacement of NH proton of the ligands by the metal ion. The keto carbonyl stretching frequency of the ligands has been depressed in

the spectra of the metal complexes by *ca.* 45 cm^{-1} . This downward shift indicates coordination by carbonyl group of the β -diketone moiety. The ester carbonyl frequency has been shifted to lower frequency by *ca.* 40 cm^{-1} indicating the involvement of ester group in chelation¹⁰. The $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{N})$ band appearing at $\sim 1525 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the ligands showed upward shift in the metal complexes and in most cases, the shifted bands coincide with the $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$ band. As a result of this upward shift, the $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{C})$ bands in the metal complexes show greater intensity or broadening. The upward shift of $\nu(\text{C}\cdots\text{N})$ on coordination to metal ion has been reported for metal chelates of some β -ketoamines and this has been attributed to enhanced chelate ring resonance on metal chelation.

Non-ligand bands appearing in the region 515–525 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and another set of bands in the range 415–425 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu(\text{M-O})$ vibrations respectively^{11,12}. Bands appearing at 318 and 250 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes can be attributed to $\nu(\text{Cu-Cl})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu-Br})$ vibrations respectively¹³. In all cases, substituted thiophene ring vibrations remain unaltered. This rules out any possibility of coordination by the ring sulphur atom. Thus the ligands acted as monobasic tridentate, coordinating through their carbonyl oxygen, ester carbonyl and deprotonated aminonitrogen.

Coordination by anion :

In view of the increasing attention on anion coordination, in metal complex chemistry, a modest attempt has been made to study the effect of various anions on antibacterial effects. Infrared spectrum of the nitrato complex showed the diagnostic bands at 1455 and 1315 cm^{-1}

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})					ESR spectra		
	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ (ester)	$\nu(\text{C=O})$ (β -diketones)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$g_{ }$	g_{\perp}	g_a
Haat	1690	1630	1525	-	-	-	-	-
Hbat	1685	1625	1522	-	-	-	-	-
Hdmt	1680	1620	1521	-	-	-	-	-
[Cu(aat)Cl]	1641	1585	1538	519	419	2.212	2.080	2.124
[Cu(bat)Cl]	1645	1582	1539	519	423	2.240	2.093	2.142
[Cu(dmt)Cl]	1640	1580	1548	521	420	2.230	2.102	2.144
[Cu(aat)Br]	1642	1590	1546	522	422	2.241	2.104	2.150
[Cu(aat)I]	1648	1588	1545	524	423	2.247	2.128	2.167
[Cu(aat)NO ₃]	1638	1580	1544	520	426	2.224	2.132	2.163
[Cu(aat)OAc]	1640	1590	1542	521	420	2.213	2.088	2.130
[Cu(aat)ClO ₄]	1644	1590	1540	520	418	2.241	2.130	2.167
[Cu(aat)(SO ₄) _{1/2}]	1640	1580	1542	522	430	2.238	2.108	2.151

for unidentate coordination by the NO_3 group¹⁴. In the acetato complex $\nu_a(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO})$ with a separation of 210 cm^{-1} indicated monodentate coordination by the acetato group¹⁵. However, the infrared spectral bands observed for the sulphato complex are more or less consistent with bidentate bonding mode¹⁶. The band at 1110 cm^{-1} (ν_3) for the perchlorate group is broad and ν_4 split into two bands with a separation of 30 cm^{-1} , which indicates a monodentate coordination by the perchlorate group¹⁷.

The electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes showed a relatively strong and intense band around 14000 cm^{-1} and a low energy less intense band appearing as a shoulder around 10200 cm^{-1} indicate a distorted tetrahedral geometry around copper(II) atom¹⁸. The appearance of the shoulder on the $d-d$ band is due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The room temperature magnetic moment values (Table 1) in the range of 1.95–1.97 B.M. also support the above geometry for the complexes¹⁹. The higher value than the spin-only value is due to spin-orbit coupling. These values also indicate that the complexes are monometallic and there is no major interaction between the unpaired electrons on different copper ions. X-band ESR spectra of the complexes in the powdered form have been recorded at room temperature and the g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values have been calculated. These values are comparable with those reported for similar type of complexes²⁰. The g_a values show that the metal-ligand bonds have considerable covalent character. From the general trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$, it is clear that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital²¹.

Antibacterial activity :

The ligands as well as the complexes have been screened for antibacterial activity^{22,23} against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *S. caure*, and the results are given in Table 3. This study reveals that the antibacterial activity of the ligands enhanced on complexation. The higher toxicity

Fig. 2

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of ligand and metal complexes

Compd.	Zone of inhibition (mm)		
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. caure</i>
Haat	12	12	14
Hbat	12	11	13
Hdmt	10	12	12
[Cu(aat)Cl]	20	19	28
[Cu(bat)Cl]	20	18	26
[Cu(dmt)Cl]	14	15	25
[Cu(aat)Br]	15	16	24
[Cu(aat)I]	14	15	25
[Cu(aat)NO ₃]	16	17	24
[Cu(aat)OAc]	16	16	22
[Cu(aat)ClO ₄]	17	16	24
[Cu(aat)(SO ₄) _{1/2}]	18	16	23

of the metal complexes can be attributed to the effect of the metal ion on the normal cell process. A possible mode of toxicity can be speculated in the light of chelation theory²⁴. Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion considerably which in turn increases the lipophilic character of the chelate and the interaction between metal ion and the lipid is favoured. This may lead to the breakdown of the permeability barrier of the cell resulting in interference with the normal cell processes. Cellular components contain a variety of functional groups that can act as metal binding ligand. For better cellular interaction, the complex should possess sufficient lipid solubility, high enough thermodynamic stability and the interaction of the metal chelate with the cells should be selective. Chelation is not the only criterion for antibacterial activity. Some other important factors which determine the activity are nature of metal ion, nature of the ligand, coordinating sites, geometry of the complex, concentration, hydrophilicity, lipophilicity and presence of other ligands. Steric and pharmacokinetic factors also play important roles in deciding the potency of an antibacterial agent.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene was prepared by a reported method³.

Preparation of ligands :

The ligands were synthesised by condensing 2-amino-3-carboxyethyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzo[b]thiophene with a β -diketone viz. acetylacetone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane in ethanolic medium in 1 : 1 molar

ratio in presence of piperidine as condensing agent.

Synthesis of metal complexes :

To a hot magnetically stirred ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the ligand (0.01 mol) added a solution of copper(II) chloride (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) in small portions. The pH of the resulting solution was maintained at 7.0–7.5. The contents were then refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The resulting solution was concentrated and cooled. The complex separated was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum. The same procedure was used for the preparation of other copper(II) complexes containing different co-ligands by using the appropriate copper salt.

References

1. J. V. Greenhill, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1977, **6**, 277.
2. P. Lue and J. V. Greenhill, in "Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry", ed. A. R. Katritzky, Vol. 67, Academic Press, New York, 1997.
3. K. Gewald, E. Schinke and H. Botcher, *Chem. Ber.*, 1966, **99**, 94.
4. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
5. H. P. Jensen, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 121.
6. G. O. Dudek and R. H. Holm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 2691.
7. N. H. Cromwell, F. A. Millar, A. R. Johnson, R. L. Frank and D. J. Wallace, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 3337.
8. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Applications of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
9. P. Gilli, V. Bertolasi, V. Ferretti and G. Gilli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 10405.
10. R. W. Hay and M. P. Pujari, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **123**, 175.
11. G. C. Perey and H. S. Stenton, *J. Chem. Soc. (Dalton)*, 1976, 2429.
12. N. Trendafilova, S. G. Nikolov, G. Bauer and R. Kellner, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1993, **210**, 770.
13. L. Chen, L. K. Thompson and J. N. Bridson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **32**, 2938.
14. B. M. Gatehouse, S. E. Livingstone and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **8**, 75.
15. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds". John Wiley, New York, 1963.
16. M. Singh, S. Hingorani, J. Srivastava, V. Puri and B. V. Agarwala, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1992, **22**, 1283.
17. V. J. Hathway, D. G. Holahand and M. Hudson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4586.
18. N. V. Thakkar and R. M. Patil, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2000, **30**, 1159.
19. T. Tokii, Y. Muto, M. Kato, K. Imai and H. B. Jonassen, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 3377.
20. L. G. Macdonald, D. H. Brown and W. E. Smith, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1982, **63**, 213.
21. J. E. Wertz and J. R. Botton, "ESR Elementary Theory and Practical Applications", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1986.
22. J. G. Collee, J. P. Duguid, A. G. Farser and B. P. Marmion (ed.), "Practical Medical Microbiology", Churchill Livingstone, New York, 1989.
23. O. E. Offiong and S. Martelli, *Il Farmaco*, 1994, **49**, 513.
24. K. N. Thimmaiah, W. D. Lloyd and G. T. Chandrappa, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **106**, 81.